

THE POLITICAL ROLE AND STATE ADMINISTRATION OF KHIVA KHANATE.

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Abstract: This article describes the administration system during the Khanate period. In this, the actions of the Khanates of Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand in the state sphere and the reforms made in the sphere of administration are presented.

Key words: Bukhara, Khiva, Kokan, centurion, ten head, governorship, central administration, Qazi soldier.

After the collapse of the Timurid Empire, Mavorunnahr was divided into three khanates. Each of these khanates has its own administration, and efforts have been made to develop a compact form of administration in the management of the state.

In the 19th century, the Khanate of Khiva was a strongly centralized state. This, in turn, opens a wide path for the development of trade and crafts. In cities such as Khiva, Khozoras, Khanka, Urganch, Kungiro, Kokhna Urganch, Shorakhan, trade and crafts develop in all aspects. From 2,000 to 5,000 people lived in these cities. 12,000 people lived in the capital city of Khiva. Each suburb is surrounded by high and defensive ramparts. Khiva khanate administratively includes Khozoras, Gurlan, Khanka, Kokhna-Urganch, Koshkupir, Pitnak, Ghazavot, Qiyat, Shohaboz, Shavat, Tashkhovuz, Ambor-manok, Urganch, Khojayli, Tomanoy, Like a call, it is divided into vices and vices. Bek and viceroys were accompanied by officials who served them.¹

The city of Khiva was personally visited by the khan and the prime minister. The internal order and tranquility of the city was under the responsibility of the head of the mirshab, the city judge for hearing criminal cases and sentencing, the head of cannon to protect the capital from accidental attacks, and the commandant (commandant) of the Ichan-Qala and Dishan-Qala. Over the years, a more perfected state system and administrative management method of the centralized military-feudal state in the Khiva khanate was established. During this period, an excellent system of administrative management was created. The political, legal, property and religious foundations of management were formed. The highest legislative, administrative and judicial power of the country gathered in the hands of the bells.

During the reign of Muhammad Rahim Khan I (1806-1825), the internecine wars in the khanate calmed down a bit and the unification of the khanate was completed. Also, the Karakalpaks and the rye-growing tribes of the Turkmens were subdued. Thanks to the reforms carried out by Muhammad Rahim Khan I, instead of the cities, which were the basis of independence in the khanate, they were divided into regional governorships, district and mosque communities. These administrative departments were closely connected with the

¹ New history of Uzbekistan. Book 1, Turkestan during the colonial period of Tsarist Russia. T. East, 2000;

central government. Initially, 15 governorships were formed in the areas on the left banks of the Amudarya. After the conquest of Tsarist Russia, the number of regional governors increased to 25. Each region is divided into mosque communities. There were a total of 1578 mosques in Khiva Khanate. The mosques were managed by the village's dignitaries-elders, mirabs and imams. They are subordinate to the governor. Hokimlar was the closest person to the khan and was considered the full ruler of the region. Governors performed tasks such as collecting taxes, maintaining order, and leading military forces. In some districts, the relations of seed production were strong. The Karakalpag and Turkmen tribes were ruled by the Inaqs, fathers and biys. The title of Inaqlik was established after the death of Muhammad Amin. In 1856-1857, the salary of the holder of this title was 400 gold, in 1858 it was 300 gold.

Abulghazi Khan allocated four places for the guests to sit during the ceremonial ceremonies.² This privilege lasted until 1873. One of the inaqs was sitting on the left side of the khan, next to Amirulumaro, and was called the great inaq. Other inoks also sat on the left side of the khan, starting from the twentieth place. In the Khiva Khanate, people with the title of paternal received a salary of 100 gold. In 1858, their salaries were increased. For example, the father received a salary of 150 gold. Father wore a sword and a knife.³

During the reign of the Khiva khanate, the khan was the supreme ruler and absolute ruler. It was considered the main residence of Taskhovli Khan in the city of Khiva. This palace consisted of one hundred and eleven rooms. Taskhovli was the residence of the khan's relatives and the center of state administrative courts. During the reign of Muhammad Rahmon Khan I, a higher administrative body - the Supreme Council - was established to strengthen the power. The Supreme Council is the main legislative body and has performed the functions of an administrative and judicial body. The meeting of the Supreme Council was held every Friday in the viewing room of the Khan's palace. The meeting was attended by the khan and his relatives, influential ayons of the palace - qushbegi, mehtar, devanbegi, naqib, sheikhulislam, chief judge and inaq, paternal and biy. In the work of the Supreme Council, the most important internal and external issues related to the life of the state were discussed and special decisions were made. The council was headed by the khan himself. Also, his will has been of decisive importance in the work of the Council.⁴

In addition, a special Council was also active in Khiva Khan's palace, which was attended by mehtar, qushbegi, devanbegi, naqib and shaykhulislam. Daily issues are resolved in this council. The Khanate of Khiva also had its own positions and titles, the total number of which was 103. The number of wage earners was 718.⁵

Khiva khanate was similar to other khanates with its management system, but it also had different aspects. The khanate had extremely diverse ranks and positions, the duties of each of them were strictly defined and salaries were paid from the state treasury. Positions exist in two directions, secular and religious positions. In the khanate, some government positions had the same character, but the salary paid to them was different.

² Yo'ldashev M.Y. Feudal land ownership and state structure in Khiva Khanate. T. 1959, p. 233.

³ Bayoniy YU.M. Shajari Khorezimshahi. T. 1991.B 56.

⁴ New history of Uzbekistan. Book 1, Turkestan during the colonial period of Tsarist Russia. T. East, 2000;

⁵ Yo'ldashev M.Y. Feudal land ownership and state structure in Khiva Khanate. T. 1959, p. 233.

References:

1. New history of Uzbekistan. Book 1, Turkestan during the colonial period of Tsarist Russia. T. East, 2000;
2. History of the peoples of Uzbekistan. T Science, 1993;
3. Yoldashev M.Y. Feudal land ownership and state structure in Khiva Khanate. T. 1959,
4. Bayaniy YU.M. Shajari Khorezimshahi. T. 1991.
5. Sadullayev A. and others. History of Uzbekistan; development of the state and society. T. Academy 2000;
6. New lines to the current problems of the history of Uzbekistan. T. Teacher, 1999;
7. google.ru